

DEMONSTRATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS EMPLOYEES

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Abstract. *Based on the study of the psychological characteristics of the formation of professional competence among employees of internal affairs bodies, practical recommendations for its development have been developed.*

Keywords: *need, activity, method, concept, competence, abilities, knowledge, skills.*

Introduction. Particular attention in the world is paid to the issue of the competence of qualified personnel with modern knowledge, independent thinking, and high-quality training of personnel working in the field of internal affairs. The most important feature of modern personnel training in the modern era is that not only the training of specialists in their field, but also the study of the socio-psychological competence of employees of internal affairs bodies is of current importance.

In empirical research, which is being carried out in a unique way around the world, one of the pressing problems remains the socio-psychological study of the problem of competence, especially the requirements for the activities of employees working in the field of internal affairs, increasing their professional, personal and intellectual potential. Although the problem of psychological characteristics of the formation of professional competence among employees of internal affairs bodies has not been studied as a subject of research, issues related to the professional competence of employees of internal affairs bodies D.U.Mamadiyarova, Yu.K.Narmetova, D.A.Scientifically researched, etc.

A person, his comprehensive maturation and well-being, the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for realizing the interests of the individual, changing outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior are the main goal and driving force of the reforms carried out in the republic. An important condition for the development of Uzbekistan is the formation of a perfect personnel training system based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal human values, based on the achievements of modern culture, economics, science, engineering and technology.

In relation to the study of the problem of professional competence in world psychology, mainly two directions are identified: professional development focused on the maturation of the individual, and focused on social aspects and factors of professional development.

The criteria for professional competence, which manifest themselves to a certain extent as a factor in the development of professional competence of an internal affairs officer, are based on the above considerations and judgments, since the manifestation and development of any manifestations of competence are directly determined on the basis of the direct influence of socio-psychological factors at various levels of the individual. Naturally, we can appreciate that the internal affairs officer and his socio-psychological and professional capabilities can serve as a perspective of competence.

The formation of professional qualities that make up the personal potential of an internal affairs officer occurs on the basis of his general development and will depend on it. In this case,

there is often a revival of existing but not in demand qualities, “awakening” and strengthening of poorly developed qualities. There is also the following dependence: the higher the level of human development, the higher his individual labor potential, the higher the quality of professional activity. On the contrary, poor development of professionally significant qualities provokes dissatisfaction with work, reduces motivation for professional development, and often leads to a change of profession.

In modern psychology, the question of the professional development of an individual, the study of his professional abilities and level of competence poses specific tasks for a number of areas of psychology. In the acmeological development of a person, her professional development also becomes important. The socio-psychological features of the manifestation and development of socio-psychological competence are a specifically complex process. Although a similar concept has found its expression in many socio-psychological literatures, it can be said, without denying this concept, that a unified scientific methodological development of the perfect level of analysis of the effectiveness of professional activity, considered only as a criterion of socio-psychological effectiveness as a means of competence, has not yet been accepted.

A.K. Markova conducted a meaningful analysis of professional competence, highlighting its procedural and effective aspects. The author systematized the structure of competence from the point of view of the process (teaching activity, pedagogical communication, and teacher’s personality) and the results of pedagogical activity, i.e., the education and upbringing of the student.

M. In Käerst research, components such as the essence of competence and its basis (abilities, talent, knowledge), human activity as a process (definitions, characteristics, signs), and results of activity (work results, changes in the object of activity) are introduced. The author included the following characteristics in the content of the competency:

- intellectual compatibility with issues mandatory for the person (employee) holding the position;
- quantity and quality of questions formulated and solved by a specialist in the main work;
- success in solving key issues;
- personality traits, manifested in the effectiveness of solving problematic issues. Here the scientist approached the concept of competence to a greater extent taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of a person.

O.A. Bulavenko suggests that competence should be considered not as a specific feature of professional activity, but as a manifested state of the individual in a steadily increased or decreased activity. We believe that competence is manifested only in active professional activity; any stagnation in activity can become an obstacle to its success.

M.D. Lapteva, in studies conducted under the guidance, the fundamental essence of competence is realized through the attitude towards the object of its application, the personal aspect of professional self-esteem, and the emotions of parental relationships. The criteria for the manifestation of competence include such as posing promising questions as criteria for assessing emotional and perceptual regulation, persistence in finding ways to solve them, the degree of adequacy of demands, self-assessment of professional competence. It turns out that the presence of these qualities, similar to those listed above, can provide a future professional with high competence.

Today in the world, special importance is attached to the following basic aspects of professional competence:

a) socially – a sense of responsibility, the ability to make joint decisions and actively participate in them, tolerance towards different ethnic cultures and religions, compliance of personal interests with the requirements of society;

b) communicative – having the ability to communicate in writing and orally in different languages;

c) a critical attitude towards social information disseminated through the media;

d) cognitive – the desire to constantly improve the level of education, the need to activate and realize one's own potential, i.e. the ability to independently acquire knowledge and skills, self-development;

e) intercultural competencies; Thus, a qualification can also be basic and vocational, as can a competence, while vocational qualifications can often also be called simple qualifications. In the scientific literature, the main qualifications include:

- non-functional knowledge, skills, individual characteristics of a person beyond the level of her professional training;

- general professional knowledge, abilities and skills, as well as abilities and personality traits necessary to perform work in the field of specific groups of professions;

- intercultural and intersectoral knowledge, skills, abilities and abilities necessary to adapt to different communities and operate effectively in them.

Emotional-volitional stability can be considered as one of the signs indicating the psychological readiness of workers for interpersonal relationships with citizens and professional activities. Emotional-volitional stability is understood as the ability to maintain a mental state favorable for successful functioning in difficult situations. Emotional-volitional stability is manifested in: - the absence of psychological reactions that give rise to uncertainty and misconceptions in the employee, reducing the effectiveness of his actions in extreme situations;

- obtaining exercises for flawless performance of professional actions in psychologically difficult conditions;

- maintain professional ingenuity, exercise reasonable caution and attention to risks, dangers, and unforeseen situations;

- do not succumb to the mental influence of persons trying to influence the strictly legal conduct of legal affairs;

- the ability to conduct a tough psychological struggle with persons who resist the prevention of crimes, their detection and investigation;

- do not lose yourself in psychologically difficult, conflict, hostile situations.

No one doubts that eliminating emotional nervousness through self-control, dispelling feelings of fear and insecurity, focusing on one point and mobilizing all forces to complete the task is a very important feature of an internal affairs officer. Frequently being in dangerous and sometimes life-threatening situations requires individuals to be able to maintain composure, quickly assess the current situation and come to optimal decisions, which contributes to more effective performance of the task, as well as further improvement of the professional activities of internal affairs bodies. The inability of an employee to control his mental state and actions negatively often leads to serious consequences for both himself and others. The inability to control one's actions reduces an individual's ability to socially and psychologically adapt to conditions

and becomes a serious obstacle to the realization of one's life potential. Employees of internal affairs bodies are daily exposed to various (most often stressful) factors. This, in turn, leads to exhaustion, exhaustion, the emergence of various negative emotional states, and shortcomings in professional performance.

Situations often arise when, during operational service, employees of internal affairs bodies will need to manage their condition. Excessive nervousness occurs when the mental and physical weight is excessive, in addition to when the employee has poor control over his behavior. This reduces the efficiency of activities and can lead to improper organization, interpersonal relationships with citizens, serious errors and shortcomings in work. Repetition of such situations often leads to professional breakdowns, loss of self-confidence, and nervous depression.

Conclusion. Despite the fact that a number of literatures examine various aspects of the socio-psychological characteristics of professional competence, it seems that there is insufficient research revealing the socio-psychological mechanisms of its manifestation and development. The competence of an individual is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that determine his flexibility in a team, embodying the structure of personality, competence, and serving to ensure the effectiveness of professional activities.

Factors influencing the manifestation and development of communicative and professional competence in an individual's professional activity influence the improvement of the level of professional skill.

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